

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 2.4

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Overview of Agroecology LLs and RIs in Europe

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
AE4EU	Agroecology for Europe
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
LL	Living Lab (Laboratory)
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing Committee on Agricultural Research
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1.1 Description of the Deliverable

This task evaluates the mapped AE initiatives that have been identified in WP2 to foster the AE transition across Europe. These have been identified and contacted after they were named by NCPs for 21 different countries (see Deliverable 2.3). The NCPs were part of various stakeholder groups (policy-makers, researchers, NGO members etc.) and asked to i) describe their opinion and experiences on the current situation of the AE transition process within their country, and ii) provide us with contact information of initiatives that in their eyes might be relevant and suitable to give feedback about their AE activities and practices through filling in an online questionnaire (link: [Questionnaire](#)) developed in WP2. This online tool was additionally sent out to the pilot network of the All-Ready project (WP3) and to the ENoLL and SCAR networks and partners. Furthermore, initiatives that were participating in the four All-Ready regional workshops during November and December 2022 were asked to provide us with information during our workshops' breakout sessions on one hand, but also through the questionnaire on the other hand. The results of the questionnaire helped and helps us to receive a general overview of organisations based on a developed score (see also 'best cases' in Deliverable 2.5) to assess their maturity within the process of AE transition. Furthermore, we were able to start an inventory of European LLs and RIs, organised regionally, and see how they perform or prioritise specific activities according to indicators and criteria regarding the extent to which initiatives contribute to agroecology transition. This was not done to rank initiatives in a specific way, to judge them or even evaluate who is 'better or worse' than another, but to understand how the current situation in Europe, in terms of diversity (geographically, maturity, AE categories/priorities) looks like.

Beside for WP2 directly, the online questionnaire and the outcomes of this deliverable (and D2.5) provide valuable and relevant information and insights for other WPs such as WP3 (development of the pilot network) and WP4 (added value of the future network). For WP3, possible candidates to expand the current size of the pilot network could be identified, while for WP4, all answers provide information on the added value of a future European network of/for LLs and RIs (e.g. prioritised activities, funding etc.).

2. Methodology

The online survey tool builds on the vision and mission of the European Network described in D1.3 and is based on the developed questionnaire which operationalises the inclusion criteria described in D1.2. The online exercise for the development of the questionnaire involved, as a first step, the extension of the geographically sensitive indicators and definitions of agroecological LLs, RIs or other OIAs developed in WP1 (D1.1 and mainly D1.2). The questionnaire then simplifies the criteria to ensure comprehension by participants who are not fully familiar with the concept of agroecology transition. Here, the questionnaire makes it possible to situate responding organisations from different regions across Europe

within the transition process, to start an inventory including an overview and illustrating the diversity of LLs and RIs.

2.1 The Questionnaire Explained

The online tool combines open and closed questions. Closed questions enable the project to understand if a specific organisation is fulfilling the criteria of agroecology transition based on our definitions (WP1), and to what extent. The open questions enable the project to collect in-depth information, and to gather examples; they are screening the main activities depicted in D1.1. Both types of questions were used to get an overview of LLs and RIs across Europe for this deliverable. A more detailed overall explanation of the questionnaire and how it is linked to various work packages and deliverables can be found in D2.1, while the background of the questionnaire can be found in D1.2. Beside open and closed questions of inclusion criteria (see detailed descriptions in D2.1 and D2.5), the questionnaire contains questions about the initiatives' funding, further if they define themselves as LL, RI or both, and in which geographical region the initiatives' main impact focuses on.

3. Overview (Inventory) of Diversity of Initiatives

In total 60 initiatives (until 11th January, 2023), filled in the questionnaire completely. The ones who did not fill in at least 75% of the questions were not considered. As stated before, this deliverable will focus on the aim to give an overview of existing LLs and RIs across Europe and pointing out the information on diversity observed so far through the questionnaire. Such as D2.5, this document in a first step was produced as a living document in July 2022. This was related to the circumstance that we did not receive a suitable number of initiatives answering the questionnaire yet. In a second step, until January 2023, some more effort was carried out (*see below and in D.2.5*) to expand the reach, and also meaningfulness of our results within this deliverable.

3.1 Number of LLs and RIs

The first important aspect for this deliverable was to see how and in which way the initiatives that filled in the questionnaire were situating themselves in the AE transition process (which was one of our main aims in developing this survey). From all the answers we received, only few did not answer this question, while the rest answered with 'yes'. This is not too surprising as we tried to make clear when we sent out the questionnaire that it was meant for initiatives that are actively fostering AE transition. It has to be admitted that we cannot prove 100% if the answers given here (and for the other questions below) were completely accurate. There might be organisations that claim to be a LL/RI and actively involved in the transition that we maybe would not define as such. However, we tried to create the questions of the survey (especially the ones about the inclusion criteria) in a way to be able to understand the activities and actual involvement of each initiative independently from how they would call or define themselves. Hence, in our eyes the answers given and the corresponding self-designation fit very well with what we were able to assess through the questionnaire.

In general, most initiatives saw themselves as either a LL, RI, OIA or something similar. 22 initiatives describe themselves as a LL, 25 as a RI, nine as an OIA and eight as other (e.g. regional administration; policy transition support; or they do not want to use the term LL for various reasons). The questions were not restricted to just one possible answer. Hence (from the initiatives above), ten initiatives that called themselves a LL would also say that they are a RI as well, while seven claimed to be a LL, RI and OIA all in one. Four initiatives called themselves a LL and OIA at the same time, two a RI and an OIA. The combination of OIA

and other was found twice while each RI and 'other', and LL and 'other' were found once. We also found a few answers without any input or stating 'uncertain'. The latter could be due to the fact that some participants (or at least the person who filled in the survey) are still not completely aware of the concept of LLs and RIs or the agroecology transition in general. This highlights the need to define and develop an overall framework in simple language and guidelines that every stakeholder is able to understand easily. The concept of AE transition often includes the concept that LLs and RIs should strongly work together. Therefore, it is rather interesting that a high number of initiatives claim to be a LL or OIA and RI at once. This would need further and more detailed investigations on how and in which way this is arranged.

3.2 Geographical Overview

In the questionnaire we received answers from initiatives located or working in 23 different European countries, most coming from France (eleven), followed by Denmark, Germany and Spain (all five). A few initiatives that are based in one country, do also conduct their work in other countries across Europe or even globally. When we divided the countries into four European regions (according to [EuroVoc](#) of the European Union), namely western, northern, southern and central-eastern, we noted that our initiatives came from seven Western European countries (France, Germany, Belgium, Switzerland, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Ireland), six from Northern European (Denmark, Norway, Finland, Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania), five from Southern (Spain, Italy, Portugal, Greece, Turkey) and four from Central-Eastern European countries (Serbia, Poland, Hungary, Slovenia). As stated before, for some countries several different initiatives provided us with information, while from other (smaller) countries we only received only information from a single organisation.

First, obviously this little overview is not representative for Europe in general as we only analysed 60 initiatives (so far). Geographically, the bias towards initiatives from Western (and partly Eastern) Europe in the number of answers for the questionnaire is linked to the fact that the mapping and contacted NCPs within WP2 contains mainly countries from these two regions (while the partner CSA, AE4EU, is mapping most countries of the other two regions). Furthermore, member initiatives within our pilot network from WP3 also consist of a higher number of participants from Northern and Western Europe. It should also be clear that members from this network show a higher motivation to fill in the questionnaire than email-contacted organisations that are not aware of the All-Ready project. During our four regional workshops, one in each region, the one in Spain covering Southern Europe was visited the best, followed by Eastern, Northern and Western Europe. Nevertheless, in countries of Eastern and Southern Europe, the language barrier was detected to be a bigger problem than in the other two regions. Therefore, a large number of participants at the workshop did not necessarily lead into a high number of replies to the questionnaire, which only exists in English language and might not always be understood easily, especially when not being familiar to the relevant terms.

3.3 Relevance of Transition Criteria and Practices

Even if the geographical information for the inventory of LLs and RIs might not show a complete picture of Europe, the answers on how the single initiatives lead or participate in specific activities fostering AE transition can certainly be interpreted for a first picture of LLs and RIs across Europe and where their priorities are manifested. Basically, every initiative stated to be actively involved as leaders, or at least participants, in co-creation activities. This is often done by bringing together farmers, but also other participants to create new ideas together, building experiments and validating the outcomes together. Potential users are involved actively and if research is conducted, often education is delivered to other partners in the real-life context. Promoting resilience and sustainability seems to be another

very important factor for the majority of the initiatives. For instance, the organisations try to convert agroecosystems to better resilience to climate change, extreme weather events and other disturbances, or help other organisations along the value chain to achieve that, while taking into account livelihoods and the economic impact of the transition process. More or less every initiative is either leading or participating in activities that support diversity. This can be interpreted in various ways. Some are involved in making land use more diverse at all scales (in fields, within landscapes, and in regions), while others are introducing increasing diversity of practices for crop production, livestock production, and other products. Furthermore, the support of the use of crops, breeds or products adapted to local conditions, diversity of diets specific practices such as crop rotation and biodiversity on different scales, seem to be of major importance. The next criterion that most initiatives considered as elementary is to support climate change mitigation as well as climate change and environmental adaptation of agricultural practices. This support can be linked to many activities, such as the use of biological and integrated pest management, the use of reduced tillage, protection of domestic pollinators, animal welfare and health as well as practices that sequester carbon on the soil or reduce greenhouse gas emissions. A bit less developed is the participation in activities that promote synergies between different functions of ecosystems. Several initiatives already lead activities while others not yet (but often are very keen to be involved in the future). Almost each of the organisations is promoting efficiency and responsibility in the use of natural resources, nevertheless, often linked to only one or two of our listed activities. While for instance, the reduced application of pesticides, veterinary drugs, fertiliser and alternative (non-chemical) soil and agronomic inputs were rather common as answers in the survey, reduced energy use and recycling of biomass and organic matter are not yet on the top of the agenda for several initiatives (but planned for the future). Finally, many initiatives are also involved in creating circular and solidarity economies, many even lead activities while others participate and only few are not at all involved yet. For example, several provide business support to shorten value chains and support food production in the region, while others focus on encouraging the demand for seasonal and regional products.

It can only be speculated why some criteria and activities are more present than others. First, it could be related to the relatively small number of current participants in the survey, as well as a geographical and cultural effect. Furthermore, some criteria are just easier to fulfil in terms of knowledge, technologies and economic input. It might be easier for an initiative (including e.g. farmers) to understand relatively simple techniques such as crop rotation or to plant cover crops, compared to long-term effects such as how to measure greenhouse gases and decrease them, or increase trophic biodiversity levels. As it was stated before, more data would be very useful for the future to make sure to obtain an overall picture across Europe with many more initiatives being involved (by filling in the survey).

4. Difficulties and Solutions to Improve and Expand the Deliverable

During the work on this deliverable, we experienced several uncertainties and problems. First, the creation of the questionnaire out of D1.2 took much longer than expected. When trying the first initial versions (e.g. within the pilot network or within the consortium of the project), it became clear that the language of the questions was too complicated and abstract for people not heavily involved within the AE transition concept. Hence, it was necessary to simplify the language and make the whole survey more straight-forward and clearer. The second problem was and still is the low number of responses that we received. Although we sent the questionnaire to a large number of people and initiatives and also hoped to gain even more answers through snow-balling effects, the number of answers remained rather

low. This might be again related to several aspects. On one hand, people (especially when reaching out to the wrong person within an initiative) might still not have fully understood many of the questions and definitions, hence ignored us. On the other hand, the questionnaire is rather long and time-consuming (thus with necessary information for the project). In general, possible participants, especially when being busy and contacted through emails, are often not very motivated to fill in an online survey completely. Finally, NCPs that have been already contacted previously or even done an interview for WP2, might have showed less effort to spread our questionnaire accordingly.

The online questionnaire will remain open and we are trying to use every possibility to further spread it whenever there is a chance that promising or relevant initiatives could fill it in. Furthermore, four more regional workshops in relation to WP4 are planned for spring 2023. During these workshops, that will again take place in all four regions of Europe (one each in the south, north, west and central-east), we are planning to work with people involved in AE networks and hope to receive some more relevant information there (even though not for this deliverable). Through face-to-face work on a co-creation base, we are expecting to receive many new insights from network leaders and funders that are very difficult to gain through online searches or even surveys (such as ours). Nevertheless, these workshops might also be a good opportunity to explain and promote our questionnaire (and the future network and partnership), so that more involved people might fill it in and provide us with additional, relevant and valuable information that could be useful for All-Ready and the future network in general. Finally, as the language barrier was mentioned above, it could be valuable to improve the simplicity of the language (again) or even translate it into various languages, which would make it easier for the participants to fill it in if they are not very familiar with the English language and especially its agroecological terms.

5. Conclusions

Altogether, with this deliverable we tried to give an inventorial overview of initiatives that foster AE transition across Europe, such as LLs and RIs. So far, we can see that several ones are rather active and on an ambitious way towards this goal, but to know more about regional diversities and problems, more information is needed. Therefore, we are planning to collect additional data to complete this picture. Nevertheless, we can already say that the questionnaire developed is a very suitable tool to find these relevant initiatives. The questionnaire proved also to be very useful in identifying suitable initiatives (LLs, RIs, and OIAs) for further engagement in subsequent tasks, e.g. analysing the added value (Task 4.1, see also D.4.1), feasible governance structures (Task 4.2) and insights into the capacity building programme of the European Network (Task 5.3). We learned more about their priorities, aims and how they define themselves, and their own work. In our eyes, this current state of the art is essential for the transition development of the future years.

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